

Wireless Power Transmission using PVBased Satellite System for Future Generation

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Abstract— Due to large population, there is a huge demand in generation of electricity. In our nature, natural resources like coal, fuel, etc. are also decreasing due to heavy use in our daily life which is unable to be renewed in a very short interval of time. Though there are power plants but the major supply of electricity is done by thermal plants run by coal which is limited in amount. Therefore, to circumvent this problem, alternative sources of energy can be achieved through the Solar Power Satellite (SPS) having high efficiency. In this work, a wireless power system is proposed containing SPS. This paper deals with the generation of power by SPS and transmitting the microwaveto earth using microwave transmitter (Magnetron) which will be converted to electricity through rectenna.

Keywords— Microwave transmitter, photovoltaic energy, rectenna, renewable energy, solar power satellite.

I. INTRODUCTION

In our daily life electricity is needed in every step. The three major categories for electricity generation are fossil fuels (coal, natural gas and petroleum), nuclear energy, and renewable energy sources. Most of the electricity is generated from thermal plant and nuclear plant. As the rise in population all around the globe creates crisis due to huge demand of natural resources. Out of this generation 60% of energy is produced by coal in thermal power station resulting emission of CO₂ causing global warming. There is a huge loss as well in transmission [2] and distribution. While transmission [2] from generating station to consumer causes 25-35% energy loss in the system due to the resistance of the wire and lowers its efficiency.

Nowadays the solar power is developing day by day and it is a renewable source of energy. So global warming and air pollution will be well maintained. We could not use the total solar energy as there is reflection and absorption in atmosphere but it is possible from the geosynchronous orbit. A geosynchronous orbit has a period proportional to the earth's rotational period. So a concept arises of Space-based Solar Power (SBSP), the concept of collecting solar power in outer space and distributing it to Earth by placing a Solar Power Satellite (SPS) into geosynchronous orbit [3]. In 1968, Dr. Peter Glaser introduced the concept of a large solar power satellite [3] system of square miles of solar collectors in high geo-synchronous orbit (GEO is an orbit 36,000 KM above equator), for collection and conversion of sun's energy

into an electromagnetic microwave beam to transmit usable energy to large receiving antennas or rectennas on earth for distribution on the national electric power grid [8].

Space-based Solar Power System essentially consists of four functional units like [6]

- A Solar energy collector to convert the solar energy into DC (direct current) electricity.
- A DC to Microwave converter.
- Large antenna array to beam the Microwave power to the ground.
- A means of receiving power on earth, for example, via microwave antennas or rectennas [1].

The paper is organized as follows: The section 2 describes the background of wireless transmission. The different components of the solar power satellite system are discussed in section 3. The section 4 describes how to convert the solar photonics into Dc power. The conversion of DC power into microwave power is demonstrated in section 5. Ground segment reception mechanism is described in section 6 and section 7 is devoted for conclusions

II. BACKGROUND OF WIRELESS TRANSMISSION

Nikola Tesla worked for Wireless Power Transmission (WPT). Wireless Power Transmission (WPT) is basically a power transmission by electrical power [2]. There is no pollution in Wireless Power Transmission (WPT) [2]. It takes the least time to transmit any power. It is more reliable than any other power transmission [2], so Wireless Power Transmission (WPT) can be done very easily. As needed it is done mostly in electrical devices as well as electronics devices. In electronic devices Wireless Power Transmission (WPT) is widely used [2]. Here the only thing is electromagnetic wave through which the power is transmitted. So, the power is transmitted without wire. It contains a microwave source and 2 antennas. The former is known as “transmitting antenna” and the later is “receiving antenna”. The microwave source consists of electron tubes which have ability of controlling the output power. It can supply power to long distant places. The antennas can transmit power in the best way due to their high efficiency and high-power handling capacity. The receiving and converting unit in a combined unit is called “rectenna” [1]. It converts microwave energy into DC electricity directly. It has a huge application in solar power satellites (SPS)[3]. The power flow diagram is shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1 Power Flow diagram

III. SOLAR POWERED SATELLITE SYSTEM

Different components in the solar powered satellite system are described in Fig.2 [3].

Fig. 2 Components of SPSS

IV. CONVERSION OF SOLAR PHOTONICS INTO DC POWERSOURCE

There are two basic methods for the conversion from photons to DC. One is from photo voltaic cell (PV cell) and the other is Solar Dynamic Method. Photo Voltaic Cells are usually used for the process, PV cells are generally made of semiconductor materials such as gallium or silicon and are made in such a way that they are capable of directly converting photons into electricity via Quantum mechanism. PV cells are usually imperfect materials because of material impurities and manufacturing defects. Currently thin film approaches are taken as they are less efficient than that of PV cells but are less costly than those and also of lightweight.

The thin films are usually made space radiation proof as in normal conditions they are less stable in radiation. There is no external structural support needed to hold it firmly like in other household uses. It is made in such a way that it becomes cheaper and also consists of less mass than usual.

V. CONVERSION OF DC POWER TO MICROWAVE POWER

It is essential to convert the DC power into Microwave power for the transmission [2] through the earth's receiving antenna. For this purpose, a microwave oscillatory device such as a Magnetron or a Klystron is used where the AC power is generated by creating a voltage difference at the antenna terminals. Magnetron is generally a tube in which the magnetizing force applied makes the electrons travel from the cathode section to the anode section through a spiral path. It is commonly seen in cyclotron type devices. Magnetrons are usually a self-oscillating device in which electrons generated at the cathode are accelerated and sent through a path towards anode. It is basically an amplifying device

but for the use in space a special type of magnetron is used. A magnetron is generally made of a cathode, an anode and a permanent magnet. The ring like anode is placed around the cathode and a powerful but permanent magnet is placed in between them which causes the generation of the required magnetic field along the length of the cathode. The cathode is heated at first causing the spontaneous emission of electrons which is known as the phenomena, the thermo ionic emission. The newly generated electrons will be readily moving towards the anode because of their negative potential but in this case, they will move in a circular path because of the presence of the crossed Electric and Magnetic field. In this case the maximum cathode voltage should be 3.7kV and that of anode should be 4.5kV. At the end terminals of the device the required microwave is collected.

A. Klystron device

There is another device by using which we can convert DC power into Microwave power. The Klystron's function is similar to that of magnetron but it has lesser use than the former one. It was invented by the Varian brothers in the year of 1937 in America. The device is linear beam vacuum tube which is generally used as an amplifier for ultra-high frequencies: The Klystron is simply a high-power amplifier which can work on upto from a few kilowatts to a few megawatts by having a working efficiency of up to 70% in average. Low power Klystrons are also available for oscillation purposes.

B. Working principle of Klystron device

The essential parts of a Klystron Device are a Cavity Resonator and some electron beams. In a two-cavity resonator device the resonators are placed parallel and the electron beams are emitted from the cathode towards the collector and when the beams reach the first resonator, the collector end has the same potential as of resonators so that the electron beams can have a constant speed throughout the process.

C. Reasons for using Klystron device over Magnetron

The following are the reason for using the Klystron device over the Magnetron.

- a) Klystron can be used both as amplifier and oscillator whereas Magnetron can only be used as oscillator.
- b) A klystron is a vacuum tube with the resonant cavities instead of input and output structures. A klystron can have internal or external feedback built in mechanism into its design. On the other hand a magnetron is quite different from a general vacuum tube in which the electron beam is forced by an external magnetic field to follow a spiral path from the cathode to the anode.
- c) Klystron has a greater stability over magnetron though magnetron has a simpler operation than the former and also can be easily handled.

VI. GROUND SEGMENT RECEPTION

While transmitting the microwave from SPS to ground a huge rectenna is placed [1]. As in Fig.3, a rectenna is a rectifying antenna - a special type of receiving antenna that is used for converting electromagnetic energy into direct current (DC) electricity.

Devices that convert AC electromagnetic waves into DC electricity are known as Rectennas. The rectenna consists of a highly efficient photonic-band-gap (PBG) structure, a microstrip low pass filter (LPF) with defected ground structure (DGS) circuitry, and a Schottky diode [1]. To evaluate the rectenna, it was fabricated on a low-cost FR-4 printed-circuit-board (PCB) material with relative dielectric constant (ϵ_r) of 4.4 in the z-direction at 10 GHz and thickness of 1mm. The rectenna achieves RF-to-DC conversion efficiency of 63% when processing received power of +18 dBm at 2.45GHz. The rectenna is a passive element with a rectifying diode, and is operated without any extra power source. The rectenna has a low-pass filter

Fig. 3 Ground receiving station

between the antenna and the rectifying diode to suppress re-radiation of higher harmonics. It also has an output smoothing filter. This demonstration rectenna consists of 6 rows of dipole antennas, where 8 dipoles belong to each row. Each row is connected to a rectifying circuit which consists of low pass filters and a rectifier. The rectifier is a Ga-As Schottky barrier diode, that is impedance matched to the dipoles by a low pass filter. The 6 rectifying diodes are connected to the light bulbs for indicating that the power is received. The light bulbs also dissipate the received power. The Earth-based receiver antenna or rectenna is a critical part of the original SPS concept. It would consist of many short dipole antennas, connected via diodes. Microwaves broadcast from the SPS will be received in the dipoles with about 85% efficiency. With a conventional microwave antenna, the reception efficiency is still better, but the cost and complexity is also considerably greater, almost certainly prohibitively so, a rectenna would be multiple kilometers across. Crops and farm animals may be raised underneath a rectenna, as the thin wires used for supporting the dipoles will only slightly reduce sunlight, or non-arable land could be used, so such a rectenna would not be as expensive in terms of land use as might be supposed. This rectenna has a 25% collection and conversion efficiency, but rectennas have been tested with greater than 90% efficiency.

Rectenna is a type of antenna which is a mechanical device which acts as a receptor and a transmitter and often functions as a guiding device for the wave path. An antenna is generally made of parabolic shape so that it reflects signals through its curved surface, it is also known as a dish type antenna. To understand its function properly, we have to consider an ideal case of antenna which is known as isotropic radiator that is a hypothetical device which has no loss of energy during signal transmission or reception. It is necessary to understand the working of an isotropic radiator minutely to completely figure out the operation of a real directive antenna [4]. So in this case it will be used as a particular reference here. The radiation intensity of the isotropic radiator is U_0 and it is expressed as

$$U_0 = P_r / 4\pi \quad (1)$$

Where, P_r is the radiated power.

Generally, Directivity of an antenna is defined as a Ratio of the intensity of radiation in a given direction radiated from the antenna to the average radiation energy over all directions.

Directivity can be written in terms of (1)

$$D = U(\theta, \phi) / U_0$$

$$D = U(\theta, \phi) * 4\pi / P \quad (2)$$

Where, $U(\theta, \varphi)$ is the intensity of radiation in the direction of (θ, φ)

Gain in the antenna is defined here as, the ratio of intensity of radiation at the required direction to the intensity of radiation [7] obtained if the power accepted by the antenna is distributed isotropically. Gain can be obtained by (2),

$$G = U(\theta, \varphi) * 4\pi / P_a \quad (3)$$

Where, P_a is the input power accepted by the antenna. Since the complete distribution of input power will not be radiated due to the presence of few types of losses, the radiation frequency will be

$$\Theta_r = P_r / P_a \quad (4)$$

Unlike other systems, the Space-based Solar Power (SBSP) systems have their own advantages and disadvantages as described below.

A. Advantages of SBSP systems

- SBSP system is totally ecosystem friendly. It is totally free from natural pollution and also doesn't cause any greenhouse effects.
- It also doesn't produce any harmful waste like nuclear power plants do.
- The major advantage of SBSP than other normal solar power plants is the solar energy is available for 24 hours and also 365 days unlike solar power which aren't available at the night time.
- For this system, the main resource needed is solar energy which is obtainable very easily from nature and also doesn't require any external support like mining of coal or supply radioactive materials like those in the thermal and nuclear plant respectively [5].
- Energy is available everywhere, so it is pretty easier to generate power in this case unlike if there is no water or air present the wind mill or the hydropower plant won't work at all [7].
- The amount of solar energy generated is huge and it will be the most essential energy source in our human civilization in the near future.

B. Disadvantages of SBSP systems

- Maintenance cost is higher and often requires specially trained personnel to handle its operation.
- To build the system, we have to carry all of the required materials from earth to space which is quite difficult and requires proper funding
- The rectenna required for the receiving purpose is huge in size and also it is difficult to maintain.

VII. CONCLUSION

The concept of Microwave Power transmission (MPT) and Wireless Power Transmission system is presented in this paper. By this method consumers would be able to get the power wireless wherever it is needed. The increasing global energy demand is likely to continue for many decades. To cope up with this demand there is insufficient natural resources. It has been predicted that by 2030, the world needs 30TW of power from renewable energy sources and solar energy alone has the capability of

generated around 600TW. This wireless solar powered satellite transmitting the power to the earth and it should be the central attraction of space and technology in coming decades. This concept bridges the gap between the existing power generation and demand. The solar cells in space achieve 24-hour sunlight and are unaffected by atmosphere and clouds. The emission of CO₂ gas levels can be minimized and brought under its permissible limit. Thus the problem of global warming will be solved to a great extent. Space solar power will be future of the world

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